

SUCCESSFUL MANAGEMENT OF GENERALIZED DEMODICOSIS IN A GERMAN SHEPHERD

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Abstract: Demodicosis is a common, inflammatory parasitic skin disease of dogs caused by the excessive multiplication of the mite, *Demodex* spp, within the hair follicles and sebaceous glands. The disease has three forms: localized, juvenile-onset generalized, and adult-onset generalized demodicosis. Successful management of this disease requires prolonged therapy due to its cell-mediated immunosuppressive nature. This case report presents a male German shepherd dog aged 1.5 years which presented with severe exudative skin lesions over the body surface. Laboratory examination of the dog's skin scraping revealed the presence of *Demodex canis* mite and spindle-shaped eggs of *D. canis*, leading to the diagnosis of generalized demodicosis. The treatment plan consisted of oral ivermectin and topical application of amitraz on the dog followed by a benzyl peroxide shampoo bath to control secondary bacterial infection. The therapy resulted in significant improvement with the moist lesions and scales disappeared, and no presence of mites on deep skin scraping. The length of *D. canis* body was measured, and the mean total body length of *D. canis* was $212 \pm 12.81 \mu\text{m}$, agreeing with previous studies. The document also discusses the life cycle of *Demodex canis* mite, diagnosis, and management of canine demodicosis. The case report aims to provide insights to veterinary professionals and researchers in the field of veterinary parasitology in the management of demodicosis.

Keywords: Demodicosis, ivermectin, amitraz, benzyl peroxide shampoo, veterinary parasitology.

Introduction

Canine Demodicosis (red mange, follicular mange) is an ectoparasitic refractory skin disease of dogs caused by the excessive multiplication of the mite *Demodex* spp in the hair follicle and sometimes in sebaceous glands. It is a dermatologic disease that occurs when mites colonize the hair follicles, sebaceous glands. Demodicosis can be localized or generalized. In generalized demodicosis dermatological changes include erythema, alopecia, follicular hyperkeratosis, pustules and crusts all over the body. Often, a secondary pyoderma further complicates the disease [5]. Generalized demodicosis may be a severe and potentially lifethreatening disease. *Demodex* mites were found in the skin of 5.4% of healthy dogs [2]. Three species of *Demodex* are involved in canine demodicosis. The most common type is *Demodex canis* and remaining two are *Demodex injai* characterized by large body and

Demodex cornei which is having a short body and about half the length of *D. canis*, also cause disease in canines [7]. The *D. canis* mite develops through four life stages: a fusiform egg, a six legged larva, an eight legged nymph, and an eight legged adult. The life cycle probably takes 20-35 days

Materials and methods

Male German Shepherd dog aged 1.5 yr presented to a field Veterinary officer, Bhadravathi, Shivamogga with a history of severe dermatitis since two months. Upon clinical examination by a Veterinarian, the dog exhibited papules, pustules, erythema, diffuse alopecia, hyperpigmentation, erosions and crusts. Distribution of lesions observed on face, around the eyes and ears, chin region, fore limbs, neck and lateral abdomen. Skin scrapings and hair plucks were collected from the affected dogs for laboratory examination. Scrapings were collected with a scalpel blade dipped in liquid paraffin and collection of scrapings was continued until there was slight oozing of blood from dermal capillaries and sent to the Department of Veterinary Parasitology, Veterinary College, Shivamogga. Skin scrapings were put into a 10% KOH and boiled for 5 minutes and centrifuged, after centrifugation sediments were collected. Few drops of sediments were added on a glass slide, a cover slip was applied over it and examined under compound microscopes with 100X and 400X of magnification for presence of mites.

Results and discussion

Canine demodicosis is a non-contagious, inflammatory parasitic skin disease of dogs characterized by excessive proliferation of commensal mite *Demodex canis* within the hair follicles and sebaceous glands [8]. Three forms of demodicosis are seen in dogs viz., localized demodectic mange, juvenile-onset generalized demodicosis and adult onset generalized demodicosis. Localized demodicosis is seen in dogs less than 1 year old. The generalized form is mostly triggered by immunosuppression. At the early stage of demodicosis alopecia and scaling of the skin is observed but when it is complicated by secondary bacterial infection it produces pustular and crusting dermatitis [4].

In the present study, the dog presented with a history of severe dermatitis since two months, upon external examination papules, pustules, erythema, alopecia, hyperpigmentation, erosions, and crusts were found on the body surface. Deep skin scraping revealed presence of carrot/cigar shaped *Demodex canis* mite on microscopic examination and spindle shaped eggs of *Demodex canis* mite were also found. Based on the history, clinical findings and laboratory examination of skin scraping the present case was diagnosed as canine demodicosis. The measurements were carried out on total body length of mites. The adult mites were measured in microns by using ocular and stage micrometers under a compound microscope. Measurement data showed, the mean total body length of *D. canis* was $212 \pm 12.81 \mu\text{m}$ which was much more than that of *D. cornei* ($132.21 \pm 14.6 \mu\text{m}$). The mean total body length of the *D. canis* mites obtained from deep skin scrapings was almost agreeable with [1] ($226.1 \pm 11.68 \mu\text{m}$) and [3] ($224 \mu\text{m}$).

Dog was treated with oral ivermectin at $400 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ for 15 days and advised the owner of dog to use amitraz (2 ml in 1 litre of water) weekly twice as topical application on dog followed by bath with benzyl peroxide shampoo up to the recovery period. For controlling secondary bacterial infection Ampicillin at $25 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$ twice a day orally, BID for 14 days was given [6]. Ten days after therapy moist lesions and scales were disappeared. Three weeks after treatment, deep skin scraping revealed less number of *D. canis* mites. One month after treatment, the general skin condition was improved and skin scraping revealed absence of mites and regrowth of hair was noticed.

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